

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YEBOAH****FIRST NAME: CHARLES****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 5%

The author used the following software: (MS Word Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The purpose of ... is to investigate the meaning of the lived experience of people to identify the essence of human experience from the perspective of the research participants.

- grounded theory
- phenomenology**¹
- ethnography
- case study

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg, and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End, Fourth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2019), 168.

2. Experienced researchers usually adopt an X, Y, and Z plan in conducting research.

X: What the researcher is working on

Y: What the researcher wants to know

Z: How beneficial the study will be to the audience or the public

Which of the following elements of research best describes X, Y, and Z respectively?

- Research topic, questions, and significance** ²
- Statistical method, data analysis, and interpretation
- Research problem, results, and conclusion
- Literature review, theoretical framework, and methodology

3. The two most common citation forms: notes-bibliography style and author-date style are often referred to as the

- APA citation style
- Chicago/Turabian citation style** ³
- MLA citation style
- IEEE citation style

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

³ Ibid., 141.

4. Which of the following statements is not true?
- Quote when the words are original or express your key concepts compellingly.
 - Summarize when details are irrelevant.
 - Paraphrase when the words express a claim you disagree with, and to be fair, you want to state it exactly.** ⁴
 - The requirement in using quotation marks is this: for four or fewer quoted lines, run them into your text, surrounded by quotation marks. For Five or more lines, set them off as an indented block.
5. Which of the following is false?
- A colon is used to connect two parts of the sentence that are logically related.
 - A semicolon is used to link two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other and each of which could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence.
 - You must add a full stop to the end of bullet points which are a list of items.**⁵
 - You must add a full stop to the end of bullet points which form a complete sentence with the preceding text.

⁴ Ibid., 77.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 18.

6. Some common Latin expressions are sometimes used in academic papers. Which of the following Latin terms applies to knowledge obtained by analyzing concepts not based on previous experience or observation?
- ad hoc
 - a posteriori
 - a priori** ⁶
 - ad lib
7. The main reason for using secondary sources does not include
- To keep up with current research.
 - To find other points of view.
 - To develop, test or justify the hypothesis or claim.** ⁷
 - To find models for the research and analysis.

⁶ Ibid., 62.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

8. All the following about style guides are true except
- They provide basic rules or features of your writing to ensure consistency and coherency in your written output.
 - They deal only with the correct usage of grammar, punctuations, and vocabulary.**⁸
 - The lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style.
 - They include trademarks or branding considerations.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

9. Consider the following statements about qualitative and quantitative research and choose the correct answers
- i. Qualitative research takes place within natural contexts, the researcher is the instrument and the methods used are flexible.
 - ii. Quantitative research studies relationships, and cause and effect phenomena.
 - iii. The emphasis on quantitative research is exploration, discovery, and description.
 - iv. Quantitative research tests or verifies theory.

From the statements above,

- Only i, and ii are correct.
- Only i, ii, and iii are correct.
- Only ii, and iv are correct.
- Only i, ii, and iv are correct.**⁹

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg, and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End, Fourth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2019), 135-42.

10. Which of the following statements about British and American English is false?

- They are both variants of World English.
- They are more different than similar especially with "educated" or "scientific" English.**¹⁰
- American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" largely due to many factors including Wealth of the US economy vs. U.K., and the magnitude of higher education in America vs. the U.K.
- They differ in national histories and cultural developments.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End. Fourth Edition*. California: Sage Publications, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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